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Dr. Vishwanath Bite

Managing Editor

Madhuri Bite

www.the-criterion.com
criterionejournal@gmail.com

C O N T E N T S**ARTICLES**

Sr. No.	Name of the Author	Title of the Paper	Download
01	Ajay Kumar	Hermann Hesse and His Pedagogical Pattern	Download
02	Ananya Mukherjee	Aborigine-Australian Voice: Reading the Poetry of Henry Kendall as a Colonial Text	Download
03	Anil Sehrawat	Autobiographical Elements in Charles Dickens' David Copperfield	Download
04	S. Anitha	Immanence and Transcendent Vision of 'The Other' Through Suffering in the Selected Novels of Patrick White	Download
05	Arun Kumar Yadav	Portrayal of Dalit Women in Bama's Sangati	Download
06	Dr. Ashok Kumar Chaturvedi	Voices of the Dispossessed in Kamala Markandaya's The Coffer Dams	Download
07	Dr. Vandana Bhatt	Issues of Identity in Bharati Mukherjee's Jasmine	Download
08	Bhavna Sharma	Translation and	Download

09	K. W. Christopher	Culture Raymond Williams and Marxist Literary Theory	Download
10	Arup Chandra Das & Dr. Smriti Singh	Discrimination and Difference, Racial and Colonial: An Overview of M.G Vassanji's The Gunny Sack and No New Land	Download
11	Dr. P. K. Debata	The Ever-Echoing Poetic Voice of Sylvia Plath through Her Works	Download
12	Deepika Rani	Melody of Sanguineness in the Poetry of Maya Angelou	Download
13	Deler Singh	Wole Soyinka and Femi Osofisan's Theatre of Protest: Struggle for a Better and Just Society	Download
14	Dr. Dipali S.Bhandari	Complications in Translation of Poetry: What Makes Poetry Untranslatable?	Download
15	Dr. Gassim H. Dohal	Teaching Le Guin's The Dispossessed	Download
16	Pamposh Ganjoo	Women and Marriage: Study of Pride and Prejudice and A Suitable Boy	Download
17	Garima Sharma	Depiction of Women Characters and Their	Download

		Resistance To Patriarchy	
18	Dr. Dashrath Gatt	Khushwant Singh as a True Secularist: A Study of His Essays and Articles	Download
19	Gollakoti Maithreyi	Reconstructing Identities through Intertextuality: A Critical Study of Thomas King's Green Grass, Running Water	Download
20	Dr. Gyanabati Khuraijam & Dr. Yumnam Oken Singh	Amitav Ghosh's The Hungry Tide: The Ebb and Flow of History	Download
21	Halis Gözpinar	Use of Proverbs in Political Discourse by US President Barack Obama and Turkish Prime Minister Recep Tayyip Erdoğan	Download
22	Archana Hooda	Plight of Afghan Women in Khaled Hosseini's A Thousand Splendid Suns	Download
23	Dr. Darsha Jani	Supernaturalism and Mysticism in Walter Scott's The Bride of Lammermoor	Download
24	M.Kalaiarasan	Concept of Machine and Human Freedom in Rabindranath Tagore's The Waterfall and Red Oleanders	Download

25	Kanwarpal Singh	Taslima Nasrin's Lajja: A Shame on Religion and Politics	Download
26	Shubhanku Kochar	Rereading, Reshuffling and Rearranging Poems: Tracing a Chronological Green Thread	Download
27	J.Hemalatha, A.Lokanayaki & Dr.K.Kumar	The Prologue of Victims	Download
28	Kusum Nandal	Forms of Violence in The Bluest Eye	Download
29	Vinayak Tukaram Kute	The Concept of the Avtaras in the Novels of Bhalchandra Nemade	Download
30	Dr. Madhu D. Singh	Playing Male-Scripted Subordinate Roles: Gender Issues in The Thousand Faces of Night	Download
31	Dr. V H Asudani & Mouli Chowdhury	Conceptualization of Love...A Comparative Study with Reference to Devdas and Madame Bovary	Download
32	G. Nageswara Rao	A Rich Kaleidoscope of Human Relations, Emotions and Experiences in Chetan Bhagat's Novels	Download
33	Dr.V. Sudhakar Naidu	Characteristics of Indian English: A Study	Download
34	Namrata Purkar	Dystopian Writing as a	Download

		Part of Science Fiction	
35	Narayan Ch. Gahatraj	Unheard Voices: Exploring the Subaltern Voices in Selected Women's Texts	Download
36	Olaniyan, Solomon O	Imagining Society in Remi Raji's Gather my Blood Rivers of Song	Download
37	Dipanwita Pal	Legendary Tales of Australian Aborigines: Finding the Reflections of Eco- Conscious through Their Myths and Legends	Download
38	Ram Naresh Patel	Re-Inventing the Self: A Reading of Bharati Mukherjee's Miss New India	Download
39	Satyajit T. Patil	Rereading an Autobiography from Ecocritical Perspective	Download
40	Prakash Bhadury	Rabindranath Tagore: A Reappraisal of His Universality and Relevance	Download
41	Dr. V.V.B.Rama Rao	Towards Wisdom Everlasting	Download
42	Ramona L. Ceciu	Missing Cities and Missing Bodies in Indian Metropolis	Download
43	Ramya. B	Parody on Ulysses- Telemachus: Father- Son Conflict in E. L. Doctorow's Loon	Download

44	Ranjana Singh	Lake: A Postmodern Perspective Dalit Women Identity in Bama's Sangati	Download
45	Renuka L.Roy	Projection of Western Womanhood in V.S. Naipaul's The Mimic Men	Download
46	Rishikesh Kumar Singh	Postmodern Psychological Aspects of Ecocriticism within/beyond the Ambit of Human Behavior	Download
47	Qudsi Rizvi & Dr. Jyotsna Sinha	Effect of Gendered Childhood on Marital Relations in Roots & Shadows	Download
48	Dr. Rohit Phutela	Kuntaka's Vakrokti Siddhanta and Girish Karnad's The Fire and the Rain: Resuscitating the Classical Indian Literary Criticism	Download
49	Ruchi Tomar	Postmodern Female Psyche with Reference to Anita Desai's Clear Light of Day	Download
50	Sachin Salunkhe	Translation Strategies in Marathi Translations of Ernest Hemingway's Novels	Download
51	Sambhaji Dattu Suryavanshi	Quality of Education in Rural Areas: Present	Download

		Status & Remedial Measures Thereto	
52	Sanjay Kumar	Social Conceptualization in the Novels of Anita Nair, Chetan Bhagat and Arvind Adiga	Download
53	K.G.B. Santhosh Kumari	A Tinge of Colonialism: Two Leaves and a Bud: Cry till Die	Download
54	Sarap N.S., Mahadik R.P. & Mehta P.G.	ESP Needs of B.Sc. (Agriculture) Students at SAUs in Maharashtra as Perceived By Teachers	Download
55	Satpal Singh & Inderjit Kaur	Modern Relevance of Gothic Fiction Focussing on The Castle of Otranto and The Monk	Download
56	Savitha Sukumar	An Ecocritical Reading of Kavery Nambisan's The Scent of Pepper	Download
57	Sayar Singh Chopra & Devendra Kumar Gora	African Culture across the World Frantz Fanon's On National Culture	Download
58	V. Selvam & Dr. S. Jeyachandra	Theme of Motherhood in Sarah Morgan Bryan Piatt's Selected Poems	Download
59	G. Serwani Venkata Swamy	Representation of Expatriation, Home and Nostalgic	Download

		Sensibility in Kiran Desai's The Inheritance of Loss	
60	Dr. Shilpi Gupta	Archetypal Imagery from the Continent to Island as Portrayed in Anita Desai's Bye Bye Blackbird	Download
61	Bijender Singh	A Feminist Study of Manju Kapur's Difficult Daughters	Download
62	Tanmoy Baghira	The Attic: An Existential Reading of Ibsen's The Wild Duck	Download
63	Tarana Bhatia	Martha Quest: Exile from Patriarchy and Quest for Identity	Download
64	Udayan Gautam	Social Realism and Blake's Songs	Download
65	Mali Ujwala Vishwas & Dr. Ghorpade Pradnya Vijay	Political Protest in Alan Paton's Ah, But Your Land is Beautiful	Download
66	Dr. Urvashi Kaushal	Representing the Ethnic Life: A Study of Vishal Bhardwaj's Adaption of The Blue Umbrella	Download
67	Usman Joshua, Agu Magret Nonyerem & Diko Ali Joshua	Transference and Preservation of Cultural Heritage in Movie Production	Download
68	Varsha Kushwaha	Promoting English for English Purposes	Download
69	Venkata Ramana Kumar .U	Human Relations, Love, Sex and	Download

		Marriage in One Night @ The Call Center	
70	Venkatesh Puttaiah	Subtexts of English in Derek Walcott, Wole Soyinka and Nissim Ezekiel	Download
71	Vidyalakshmi A.C	Quest for Identity, Desire and Dreams – the Resistance to the Consumerist Ideology in Fight Club, a Psychoanalytic Study	Download
72	Vijay Mehta	The Strength of the Arabian Life-Style Depicted in Jean Sasson's Later Novels	Download
73	Vikas Yadav Raskar	Cultural Conflicts and the Empowerment in Amulya Malladi's The Mango Season	Download
74	Darakhshan Zafar	Use of Formulaic Expressions: A Strategy to Promote Oral Fluency among ESL Learners	Download
75	R. Renuka Narasiman & Prof. Vinita Singh Chawdhry	Balram's Quest for Freedom in Adiga's <i>The White Tiger</i>	Download
76	M. Sivapriya	The Manipulation of Words in Richard Newman's Briefcase of Sorrow: A Stylistic Approach	Download
77	Sakshi Wason	Isadora Duncan and	Download

		Modernism	
78	Surajit Sen	Credibility of Women Characters in the Selected Tragedies of William Shakespeare	Download
79	Dr. Ruby Rani	Bertrand Russell and Aldous Huxley: A Comparative Study of Scientific Fiction	Download
80	Pallavi Thakur	Social Conditioning: A Politics of Gender in The Blind Assassin	Download
POETRY			
01	Afzal Moolla	To the Nameless Soldier	Download
02	Muneer Azad	Nothing Remains	Download
03	Dušan Gojkov	She	Download
04	Santanu Halder	Divine Glory Lost	Download
05	Indrani Bhattacharya	Between Us....	Download
06	J. D. Isip	Envy's Child	Download
07	Dr. C. Muralidara Kannan	Licensed to Live Everywhere	Download
08	Dr. Katta Rajamouly	Inklings-Saplings	Download
09	Afzal Moolla	We shall always be Many More	Download
10	P. Nasarudheen	On Divorce	Download
11	Piya Chakrabarti	The Prisoners of Andaman	Download
12	Ravi Naicker	Rhino – Open Season	Download
FICTION			

01	Christine Ottoni	This Did Not Happen	Download
02	Ezeiyoke Chukwunonso	My Father's Beer	Download
03	SK Kalsi	Kuchaji	Download
04	Ramesh Tiwari	A Wad of Notes	Download
05	Sujatha Gopal	Liberation	Download
Book Reviews			
01	Dr. Vishwanath Bite	The Unheard I By Kiriti Sengupta	Download
02	Dr. Pradip Kumar Patra	Silent Days : Poems by Jaydeep Sarangi	Download
03	Prof.G.Geethanjali	The Steve Jobs Ways By Jay Elliot	Download
04	Dr.Anshu Raina	And the Mountains Echoed By Khaled Hosseini	Download

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